

VI International Forum on Teacher Education

The Relationship of the Characteristics of “Perezhivanie” (Experiencing) in the Process of Knowledge Assimilation in the Lecture Classes of Young Students

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Abstract

The report is devoted to the urgent problem of modern education - the substantive aspect of educational activity: the problem of mastering knowledge in higher education. The assimilation of knowledge is the main central system-forming phenomenon in the educational process (Zimnyaya, 2000). The professional development of students depends on the effectiveness of learning. We consider the internal plan of the learning situation through the study characteristics of «perezhivanie» (experiencing) in the process of mastering knowledge during a lecture. We relied on many research years of the experiencing of Fakhrutdinova's research in the field of psychology (2008, 2009, 2012), where the structural characteristics of «perezhivanie» (experiencing) - energy, spatial, temporal, informational, as well as functional characteristics - the developing function of “perezhivanie” (experiencing) are revealed. The trigger of «perezhivanie» (experiencing) is the impression.

The purpose of the study is to analyse the relationship between the characteristics of “perezhivanie” (experiencing) in the process of knowledge assimilation in the classroom lecture type of students. As the leading method Fakhrutdinova is leading the research method It was revealed that the energy, spatial, temporal, informational characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) have a high level of values, which indicates the high developing potential of lecture classes. Students also noted a high level of interest, the importance of lectures, their usefulness for their professional development, and high values of the characteristics of the impression of a lecture were observed. There was a high level of concentration on the contents of the lecture, and students noted high levels of concentration. The results show that lecture classes are important in the assimilation of knowledge since they provide high values of trace and information-energy, spatio-temporal characteristics of “perezhivanie” (experiencing) in the process of knowledge assimilation. The correlation activity of the energy characteristics of “perezhivanie” (experiencing) in the process of knowledge assimilation is revealed. Lecture classes have a high developing potential in the professional development of students.

Keywords: “perezhivanie” (experiencing), educational activities, knowledge assimilation, higher education, learning motivation.

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Published by Kazan federal university and peer-reviewed under responsibility of IFTE-2020 (VI International Forum on Teacher Education)

Introduction

The problem of the efficiency of learning is central to the psychology of educational activity, since it is the basic concept of all theories of learning (teaching, learning) (Rubinstein, 1989; Zimnyaya, 2000). The quality of the assimilation of knowledge in higher education institutions by young students is of great importance to the future of modern society. We consider this problem in the context of the internal plan of the situation of educational activities of young students (Vygotsky, 2000).

The experimental base of the study was Kazan (Volga region) Federal University. The subjects were 34 students aged 21 to 28 years old. Methods for studying the structural organization experiencing of knowledge assimilation process in the educational activities of young students was "Questionnaire of "perezhivanie" (experiencing)" of Fakhruddinova (2012), including the following scales: "Energy characteristics", "Spatial characteristics", "Time characteristics", "Information characteristics" of "perezhivanie" (experiencing). Also, questionnaires of readiness for mastering knowledge. (Fakhruddinova, 2008, 2009, 2012). The "Questionnaire of" "perezhivanie" (experiencing)" measures spatial, temporal, energy, and informational characteristics. (Fakhruddinova, 2012).

The scale "Energy characteristic" reflects the intensity, strength, brightness, power of the subject's experiencing. High scores on this scale indicate that the subject is experiencing very intense, energetically charged experiencings. Low indicators reflect sluggish experiencings of very low intensity, the lowest indicators reflect that in fact, what is happening in the subject does not cause any experiencings.

The scale "Spatial characteristic" shows the volume, breadth and depth of the experiencing of the inner life of a person. High values on this scale mean that the subjective world is filled with experiencing. If we compare it with a fire in a room: the fire of the fire engulfed almost the entire room. Low values on this scale mean that the subject gives this experiencing a small place in his inner life. In his inner life there are many more other more important inner events for him.

The scale "Time characteristic" means how this experiencing influences the course of internal time. High values show that this experiencing causes a subjective feeling of acceleration of time, its saturation with

events. Time passes quickly and imperceptibly. A very high level of temporal characteristics is associated with the feeling that the subject simply does not keep up with the time, cannot control the events that are happening too quickly. The time sequence for him is violated, he is lost in this stream of events. Low values mean that the events experienced cause a feeling of time slowing, its plagues and excruciatingly slow passage. But at the same time, this indicator can mean falling out of the time stream, detachment from what is happening, contemplation.

The scale "Information characteristic" shows the significance of a given experiencing for the subject, the degree of personal involvement in what is happening, how much this experiencing changes, knowledge gives. High indicators reflect the very high significance of the experiencing for the subject, its high informational richness. The subject feels how this experiencing changes him. Low indicators mean that this experiencing is not enough, which gives the subject in terms of experiencing, knowledge, information. It is of little significance to the subject.

The author's questionnaire of readiness for mastering knowledge includes the scales of "Interest", "Significance", "Usefulness", "Recollection" and reflects the motivational aspect of experiencing learning activities. The scale "Interest" shows how interesting this lecture is for students. High values indicate a high level of interest, low values correspond to a low level of interest. The "Significance" scale shows how much this lecture is defined as significant for future professional activities. High values indicate a high level of significance, low values correspond to a low level of significance. The "Usefulness" scale reflects how much the acquired knowledge is determined by students as useful for future professional activities. High values indicate a high level of utility, low values correspond to a low level of utility. The "Recollection" scale reflects the level of concentration of attention. High values indicate a high level of concentration, low values correspond to a low level of concentration.

During a lecture-type lesson, students were handed out the "Questionnaire of "perezhivanie" experiencing" and the questionnaire of readiness to master knowledge. At the beginning of the lesson, students filled out a questionnaire of readiness to assimilate knowledge, then they determined their characteristics of experiencing in the process of assimilating knowledge at the beginning, middle and end of a lecture-type lesson using the "Questionnaire of "perezhivanie" experiencing" by Fakhruddinova.

The research revealed reliable relationships between the readiness to assimilate knowledge and the characteristics of experiencing educational activities during the entire lesson of the lecture type. A high level of readiness for the knowledge assimilation and a high developmental potential of experiencing educational activities in a lecture-type lesson were also revealed.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to analyze the structural relationships of experiencing the process of assimilation of knowledge in the educational activities of students:

1. To study the willingness to assimilate the knowledge of students.
2. To study the spatio-temporal and information-energy characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of the process knowledge assimilation in the educational activities of students.

Literature review

The methodological basis is the subjective, subject-activity approach, developed in the works of Russian scientists (Rubinstein, 1989; Brushlinsky, 2003; Znakov, 2005). We are investigating the internal, subjective plan of educational activity, which is an internal plan of the development situation of students (Vygotsky, 1987). The nature of the experiencing has been described by Fakhruddinova in the English-language literature (2010). Based on the theory of “perezhivanie” (experiencing) (Fakhruddinova, 2008, 2009, 2012), we examine the characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of learning activities as manifestations of the internal plan of learning activities. We study the characteristics of experiencing the knowledge assimilation process in lecture-type classes in higher educational institutions.

The research problem is the insufficient knowledge of the infrastructural relationships of the experiencing of learning activities in knowledge assimilation process in lecture-type classes in higher educational institutions.

The problem of learning activities experiencing is considered in the articles of Fakhruddinova and Sabirov (2017). Studies have shown that the structure of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of learning activities of schoolchildren differs depending on the cultural and historical context. The theory of experiencing of Fakhruddinova (2009) shows that experiencing in mental activity has developing functions. A structural analysis of the experiencing of the process of mastering the knowledge of students can show the current situation of the educational process in a modern institution of higher education in a subjective context. Impression is the trigger mechanism of “perezhivanie” (experiencing) and is included in the structure of experiencing (Fakhruddinova & Sabirov, 2012, 2018, 2019). At the moment, the structural relations of the characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of the process of knowledge assimilation in the educational activities of students are not well understood.

Results

The results of descriptive statistics (average values) of the knowledge readiness questionnaire are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Average values of indicators of readiness for mastering knowledge in the class of the lecture type of student youth.

Legend: 1 - indicators of the scale "Interest", 2 - indicators of the scale "Significance", 3 - indicators of the scale "Utility", 4 - indicators of the scale "Recollection".

Figure 1 shows that all indicators of the questionnaire have high values, which indicates a high willingness of students to learn knowledge. Especially high are the indicators of the scales "Significance" and "Interest", which shows a high motivational readiness for lectures, which are presented to students as interesting and significant for their future profession.

Figure 2 shows the characteristics of the "perezhivanie" (experiencing) of the process of mastering knowledge in the educational activities of students during the lecture type.

Figure 2. Dynamics of the average values of the spatio-temporal and information-energy characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of the process of assimilation of knowledge in the lecture class of student youth.

Legend: 1 - indicators of the scale “Energy characteristic”, 2 - indicators of the scale “Spatial characteristic”, 3 - indicators of the scale “Time characteristic”, 4 - indicators of the scale “Information characteristic” of the “Questionnaire of “perezhivanie” (experiencing)”. Row 1 corresponds to the values of the characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of learning at the beginning of the lecture, row 2 - in the middle of the lecture, row 3 - at the end of the lecture.

Figure 2 shows that the indicators of energy, spatial, temporal and informational characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of the process of assimilation of knowledge are above average, which means high efficiency of assimilation of knowledge in the lecture class. We also observe that the level of characteristics is stable during the lesson, which means a high developmental potential of the lecture-type lesson throughout the entire duration of the lesson.

A correlation analysis of the infrastructural relationships of learning “perezhivanie” (experiencing) is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Correlation relationships of the structural components of the learning “perezhivanie” (experiencing).

		Interest	Relevance	Utility	Recollection
The beginning of a lecture	Energy characteristic	–	–	r=0,506, p=0,003	r=0,517, p=0,002
	Spatial characteristic	–	–	–	–
	Temporary characteristic	–	–	–	–
	Informational characteristic	–	–	–	–
The middle of a lecture	Energy characteristic	–	–	–	–
	Spatial characteristic	–	–	–	–
	Temporary characteristic	–	–	–	–
	Informational characteristic	–	–	–	–
The end of a lecture	Energy characteristic	–	r=0,444, p=0,01	–	–
	Spatial characteristic	–	–	–	–
	Temporary characteristic	–	–	–	–
	Informational characteristic	–	–	–	–

Legend: On the horizontal scale of the questionnaire of readiness for assimilation of knowledge, on the vertical scale of the "Questionnaire of “perezhivanie” (experiencing)".

From table 1 it can be seen that there are reliable relationships between the motivational component of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of learning activity manifested through the scales of the questionnaire readiness for learning and spatial and temporal characteristics of learning activities, which shows the presence of the influence of readiness for learning affects the processes of learning activities in the learning process . The results showed the correlation activity of the energy component of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing), which shows its relationship with the motivational component of the

activity. Studies have shown that the willingness to master knowledge leads to an increase in the energy component of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of learning activities throughout the lecture class.

Discussions

From Table 1 it can be seen that there are reliable relationships between the motivational component of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of learning activity manifested through the scales of the questionnaire readiness for learning and spatial and temporal characteristics of learning activities, which shows the presence of the influence of readiness for learning affects the processes of learning activities in the learning process . The results showed the correlation activity of the energy component of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing), which shows its relationship with the motivational component of the activity. Studies have shown that the willingness to master knowledge leads to an increase in the energy component of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of learning activities throughout the lecture class.

Conclusion

The research problem is the insufficient knowledge of the infrastructural relationships of the learning “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of student youth in the process of mastering knowledge in the lecture class. The result of the study is the identification of reliable correlation relationships between the structural components of experiencing the process of assimilation of knowledge in the lecture class. The correlation between the willingness to assimilate knowledge and the characteristics of experiencing the process of assimilation of knowledge is revealed. High readiness for the assimilation of knowledge was revealed, especially in terms of the significance of the lesson for the future profession and the degree of interest in the topic of this lecture. High values of the indicators of the spatio-temporal and information-energy characteristics of experiencing the process of knowledge assimilation in the educational activities of students throughout the lecture are revealed. Studies have shown the high efficiency of lecture-type classes in mastering the knowledge of students.

Acknowledgements

The work is performed according to the Russian Government Program of Competitive Growth of Kazan Federal University.

References

Brushlinsky, A. V. (2003). *Psychology of the subject*. Saint Petersburg: Aleteya.

- Fakhruddinova, L.R. (2008). *Psychology of human experiencing*. Kazan: Publishing house of Kazan State University.
- Fakhruddinova, L. R. (2009). *Theory of Experiencing*. Kazan: Publishing house of Kazan State University.
- Fakhruddinova, L. R. (2010). On the phenomenon of “Perezhivanie”. *Journal of Russian & East European Psychology*, 48(2), 31-47.
- Fakhruddinova L. R. (2012). *Structural-dynamic organization of the subject's experiencing* (Doctoral dissertation). Kazan: Kazan Federal University.
- Fakhruddinova, L. R., & Sabirov, T. N. (2017). Cross cultural studies of learning activities experiencing Russian and Chinese teenagers. *QUID-INVESTIGACION*, 25, 141-147. Retrieved from <http://revistas.proeditio.com/iush/quid/article/view/1727>
- Fakhruddinova, L. R., & Sabirov, T. N. (2017). Cross-Cultural Studies of Structural and Dynamic Features of Learning Experiencings among Russian and Chinese Teenagers. *HELIX*, 8(1), 2527- 2530. Retrived from: <http://www.helix.dnares.in/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/2527-2530.936.pdf>
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1987). *Psychology*. Moscow: Ripol Classic.
- Rubinstein, S. L. (1989). *Fundamentals of General Psychology: in 2 volumes*. Moscow: Pedagogika.
- Zimnyaya, I. A. (2000). *Educational Psychology*. Moscow: Logos.
- Znakov V. V. (2005). *Psychology of human existence and self-understanding of the subject*. Krasnodar: Kuban State University.